

KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDES AND PRACTICES OF GRADE SCHOOL LEARNERS ON SOLID WASTE MANAGEMENT

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 26

Issue 5

Pages: 418-428

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2476

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13909295

Manuscript Accepted: 09-10-2024

Knowledge, Attitudes and Practices of Grade School Learners on Solid Waste Management

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Abstract

The study aimed to determine the level of awareness of the grade four, five and six learners of St. Therese de Avila Learning Center of Poblacion, Iligan City in relation to their solid waste management practices during the School Year 2019 - 2020. This study used descriptive - correlation design that describe the correlation of the two variables which were the level of awareness on solid waste management of the respondents in terms of knowledge and attitudes and their practices in waste segregation, reduce, reuse, recycling and disposal. The hundred thirteen (113) learners from St. Therese de Avila Learning Center were the subjects. The Pearson Moment of Correlation was used to find out the significant relationship between the respondent's level of awareness and practices in solid waste management. The hypothesis on the relationship between the level of awareness in terms of knowledge and the segregation, reduce, recycling and disposal practices of respondents was rejected. However, there was a significant relationship between the level of awareness in terms of knowledge and the reusing practices of the respondents. It also revealed that the hypothesis on relationship between the level of awareness on solid waste management in terms of attitude and the segregation, reduce, reuse and disposal practices of the respondents was rejected. However, the hypothesis on the relationship between the awareness in terms of attitudes and reducing practices of the respondents was not rejected. An action plan regarding on solid waste management was presented for implementation.

Keywords: *knowledge, attitudes, practices, grade school learners, solid waste management*

Introduction

Wastes are produced either directly or indirectly by the actions of learners in schools. The amount of solid trash in the school community will grow significantly in the future due to population growth. To properly play their part effectively in waste management, learners must be aware of the environmental issues surrounding the growing amount of garbage disposal and its treatment, which pose major challenges to human ecology. Educating the next generation about their surroundings is one method to contribute to the preservation of Mother Earth.

Solid waste management is a dynamic, multifaceted problem that calls for solutions that are specifically designed to fit the particulars of each city or region. It goes beyond the simple chore of gathering and disposing of waste. Waste management is one of our problems not just here in the Philippines but also other countries. Mismanagement of waste has genuine environmental consequences: ground and surface water contamination, air pollution, exposure to toxins, and spread of disease. Indeed, even to the casual observer, solid waste's environmental, human health, and aesthetic impacts in Philippine city areas are substantial. Solid waste is not speculated to be the biggest problem if all consumers are knowledgeable enough about how to dispose of solid waste.

According to Castillo et al. (2013), the global community recognized that Solid Waste Management (SWM) is an issue that requires serious attention. The aggressive pursuit of economic growth, by developing countries like the Philippines, has resulted in the manufacture, distribution, and use of products and the generation of waste that contributes to environmental degradation and global climate change. Available data showed that the Philippines ranked 9th among the countries at risk from climate change due to rise of sea levels, intense storm surges, and droughts.

This is clearly seen in the nation's frequent and severe floods brought on by powerful typhoons, which many attribute to climate change. In addition to the nation's economic development, waste management has become a significant environmental concern due to the country's rapid population expansion. With an annual growth rate of 1.87%, the Philippine National Statistics Office (NSO) projected that the country's population was approximately 97 million in 2012. This number places the Philippines as the 12th largest nation in the world as of right now. The Ecological Solid Waste Management Act of 2000, the local government units (LGUs) in the country hold the primary responsibility for effective and efficient solid waste management. Despite this law, however, poor solid waste management in the Philippines is still prevalent since open and controlled dumps are being used in the country. This poses great threats on the country's environment and public health that include: a) alteration of physical and chemical properties of soil due to percolation of landfill gases (CO₂ and CH₄) and leachates from unsanitary landfills and open dumps; b) objectionable odor; and c) soil and groundwater pollution. But the gravest problem now in the country is the scarcity of new landfill sites for the growing number of garbage generated by the Filipinos (Castillo et al. 2013).

Premakumara et al. (2014) study implied that if LGUs have a high level of political commitment, plan and develop collaboratively effective local strategies to meet local conditions, build partnerships with other stakeholders, develop capacity, secure sufficient funding and incentives, and closely monitor and evaluate performance, the impacts of the national mandate can be realized.

In Iligan City, the growing issue of improper solid waste management is becoming a threat to the social, environmental, and health

security in the community. It obstructs the chance to build a well and better society. The ineffective waste collection and inadequate disposal facilities bother concerned town folks. The gathering of solid wastes becomes ineffective when individuals in their homes won't participate and segregate properly their trash employing that they easily blame the government for inefficiency when they themselves are not cooperating (Magallanes, 2011).

Some universities implemented the "Clean as You Go" (CLAYGO) policy to strengthen the academic component and students' awareness of environmental issues and their response to the garbage problem on campus. The aforementioned institutional initiatives aimed at forming all members of the academic community "advocates of a sustainable environment" (Ahmad et al., 2015).

Nowadays, the government and non - governmental groups help in preventing the worsening condition of the environment. They try their best to minimize the problem of solid waste by educating the young ones. It is an urgent need to educate young minds to environmental problems and concerns.

Environmental education is a way to teach learners about environmental issues and concerns. This can be integrated into lesson plans for all grades and subject areas to help learners learn how to make sound choices about the environment. Through what the learners learned they can integrate changes in the environment. This is the reason why they are selected to be the respondents of the study.

With the present reality of the situation, the researcher was conducted a study on Grade IV to VI learners to determine the level of awareness and practices in solid waste management and how far they are aware and knowledgeable about solid waste management. The researcher aimed to educate the learners about the effects of improper solid waste management on their health and environment and to some extent prompt some ways in which to enhance their solid waste management. Eventually, through this study, it can help them to be more conscious of protecting our environment.

The study was conducted at St. Therese de Avila Learning Center during the second semester of the school year 2019 – 2020. The researcher is credible to conduct this study since she is a teacher in profession and has been teaching Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) in Grades IV to VI and other subject areas for five years in the said school.

Research Questions

The main thrust of this study was to determine the level of awareness of the learners in relation to their solid waste management practices. Specifically, it sought to answer the following:

1. What is the level of awareness on solid waste management of the respondents in terms of;
 - 1.1. Knowledge; and
 - 1.2. attitudes?
2. What are the solid waste management practices of the respondents in terms of;
 - 2.1. segregation;
 - 2.2. reduce;
 - 2.3. reuse;
 - 2.4. recycling; and
 - 2.5. disposal?
3. Is there a significant relationship in the level of knowledge on solid waste management and the practices on the solid waste management of the respondents?
4. What action plan on solid waste management can be formulated based from the results of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

The researcher used the descriptive-correlational research design using elementary learners as the respondents and adapted the questionnaire as the main tool in gathering the data. Descriptive design was used to describe the level of awareness in terms of knowledge and attitudes and practices of the respondents on solid waste management. In this study, a correlation research design will be used to find out if there is a significant relationship between the level of awareness and practices of the students on solid waste management.

Respondents

Table 1. *Number of Respondents by Grade Levels*

Respondents	Section	Male	Female	Total of Respondents
Grade IV	I	11	10	21
	II	14	8	22
Grade V	I	6	11	17
	II	13	7	20
Grade VI	I	9	11	20
	II	9	4	13
Total		62	51	113

The respondents of the study were the Grade IV, V, and VI learners of St. Therese de Avila Learning Center in Iligan City, Lanao del Norte. Each grade level is composed of two sections. Complete enumeration was used in taking the respondents of the study since all grade IV, V, and VI learners were considered as respondents. There were 62 males and 51 females or a total of 113 learners in all served as respondents.

Instrument

Two sets of adapted questionnaires from Alimona (2017) and Paghastian (2017) were used in this study. The first questionnaire was concerned about the level of awareness of the learners towards solid waste management. The questions are based on R.A 9003 (Philippine Ecological Solid Waste Management Act of 2000). Moreover, the first questionnaire is multiple choices which consisted of fifteen (15) items. Each item consisted of four (4) choices that were closely related and the respondents were asked to encircle the letter of their choice.

The second questionnaire dealt with solid waste management practices. It consisted of descriptors which were the solid waste management practices in terms of segregation, reduce, reuse, recycling, and disposal. The questionnaire was in a Likert Scale form with the corresponding answers and points as follows {Always (4), Often (3), Seldom (2), and Never (1)}. The learners were asked to put a checkmark on the column that corresponds to their practices.

On the questionnaire on the level of awareness on solid waste management regarding their knowledge, the scoring procedure for multiple choice corresponds to 1 point given for every correct answer. On the level of awareness on solid waste management regarding their attitude, the scoring procedure is based on the following: 4 means strongly agree, 3 means agree, 2 means disagree, 1 means strongly disagree. On the solid waste management practices questionnaire, each of the practices has five (5) statements which is usually done by the respondents. It has four (4) qualities {Always (4), Often (3), Seldom (2), and Never (1)} with a rating of 4 points for answering “always”, 3 points for “often”, 2 points for “seldom”, and 1 point for “never”.

Procedure

To facilitate the gathering of data, permission to conduct the study was obtained by the researcher from the school administrator, principal, and teachers of St. Therese de Avila Learning Center. The communications were signed and approved by the concerned personalities.

The researcher presented to the respondents the nature of the study and formally administered the test with an attached copy of the letter to the respondents approved by the school administrator. The respondents answered the questionnaire during TLE period which was facilitated by the researcher.

The instruction on how to answer the two sets of questionnaires was explained to the respondents. During the distribution of the questionnaire to the respondents, the researcher assured the respondents of the confidentiality of their answers.

Data Analysis

The data was tabulated and interpreted to acquire the actual information needed. The following statistical tools were employed to answer the different problems presented:

Problem 1. Frequency and Percentages were used to analyze the score in the knowledge test about solid waste management.

Problem 2. Weighted Mean was used to determine the solid waste management practices of the respondents.

Problem 3. Pearson Product Moment of Correlation was used to determine the significant relationship between the level of awareness on solid waste management and the practices on solid waste management of the respondents.

All the computations were done manually or with the statistics software of an accredited statistician.

Results and Discussion

This section discusses the data that were shown in the tables and graphs. The data were analyzed, interpreted, and supported by related literature or studies.

Problem 1: What is the level of awareness on solid waste management of the respondents in terms of knowledge and attitude?

Table 2. *Level of Awareness on Solid Waste Management of the Respondent in Terms of Knowledge*

Score Percentage	Performance Category		
		F	%
75% - 100%	Very Aware	72	64.00
50% - 74%	Aware	34	30.00
49% and below	Not So Aware	7	6.00
	Total	113	100

As shown in Table 2, comparatively speaking, only 64% of respondents are well aware of solid waste management, while 6% are not. This means that most of the respondents show a higher level of awareness compared to the 6 % of the respondents.

According to Barton (1990), managing solid waste is essential to preserving the environment and public health. Transporting, treating, and disposing of garbage in an inexpensive, efficient, and hygienic manner are the objectives of good solid waste management. Knowledge is essential to every human being, most importantly if it involves health-related understanding. Acquiring comprehensive knowledge and comprehension of appropriate solid waste management can aid in mitigating health issues and eradicating infectious diseases that arise from inadequate waste management. However, improper solid waste management practices can have a negative impact on an individual's health as well as the environment.

In a facility such as the St. Therese of Avila Learning Center, waste management has grown increasingly difficult. The findings indicate that, even in cases where the respondents had some awareness of solid waste management, comprehensive instruction, integration, and execution must take place within the school premises to provide sufficient training on the subject.

Table 3. *Attitude on Solid Waste Management of the Respondents*

<i>Attitude</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
A1: I understand that burning of waste materials like plastic and other synthetics will weaken the ozone layer.	3.12	Agree
A2: Improper garbage disposal can create health risks.	2.56	Agree
A3: I am concerned about the undesirable impacts of dumping garbage to streets and drainage.	3.15	Agree
A4: I am familiar with the processes of garbage segregation.	3.12	Agree
A5: I am alarmed about the adverse impacts of throwing garbage to rivers and other waterways.	3.16	Agree
A6: I am interested in participating seminars about recycling of waste materials.	3.15	Agree
A7: I am interested in engaging on composting training sessions.	2.81	Agree
A8: I am aware about the law regarding solid waste management.	2.95	Agree
A9: I attend seminars regarding the recycling of materials.	2.85	Agree
A10: Waste segregation is important to me.	3.31	Agree
Average	3.02	Agree

Note: 1.00-1.79, Strongly Disagree; 1.80-2.59, Disagree; 2.60-3.39, Agree; 3.40-4.00, Strongly Agree

As shown in Table 3 (Fig), the amount of awareness and attitude of the respondent regarding solid waste management. Items ten and two had the highest and lowest weighted means, respectively, with a description of "agree" and 3.21 and 2.56, respectively, and 3.02, the average result, and "agreed" comments. This implies that the majority of participants are cognizant of regulations pertaining to solid waste management and suitable methods for segregating waste.

According to Ajzen's (1991), theory of Planned Behavior, a person's intentions to perform and engage in the behavior are influential whether he or she engaged in the behavior. A combination of perceived behavioral control, attitude toward the behavior, and the subjective norm results in behavioral intention. The degree to which a person can control their conduct relies on how hard they believe the activity will be to perform. The more favorable a person's attitude is toward behavior and subjective norms, and the greater the perceived behavioral control, the stronger that person will intend to perform the behavior. Respondents' concern for appropriate solid waste management is indicated by their favorable attitude. Their goal is validated and their subjective norms are satisfied by this attitude.

Problem 2: What are the solid waste management practices of the respondents in terms of waste segregation, reduce, reuse, recycle and disposal?

Table 4. *Level of the Solid Waste Management Practices of the Respondents in Terms of Waste Segregation*

<i>Waste Segregation</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
WS1: I segregate biodegradable waste (paper, banana peel, cardboard and vegetables) and non-biodegradable (plastic toys, glass, steel rubber) waste at school.	3.66	Always
WS2: I separate recyclable wastes (paper, cardboard, plastic bottles) from non-recyclable (food wastes, leaves, twigs) waste at school.	3.25	Often
WS3: I separate non-harmful wastes from toxic and hazardous wastes such as pentel pens, laboratory chemicals, ink, cell batteries and others.	3.05	Often
WS4: I mix all the garbage in one container. (according to its classification)	3.45	Always
WS5: I segregate recyclable items for collection.	3.04	Often
Average	3.29	Often

Note: 1.00-1.79, Never; 1.80-2.59, Seldom; 2.60-3.39, Often; 3.40-4.00, Always

As shown in Table 4, the item that received the highest weighted average of 3.66 was: I separate rubbish at school into biodegradable (paper, cardboard, banana peels, and vegetables) and non-biodegradable (plastic toys, glass, and steel rubber). The weighted mean average of 3.29 was also recognized as supporting the notion that the respondents had appropriate segregation methods for solid waste management. In addition to often sorting recyclable materials for collection, the respondents separate waste that is both biodegradable

and non-biodegradable.

Waste segregation must be implemented at the source to avoid contamination or mixing of the different waste components, which could make straightforward recycling difficult. Furthermore, chronic diseases are caused by waste workers and rag pickers directly touching or sorting garbage or solid waste. Therefore, recycling and resource reuse of separated materials are ensured and encouraged by sorting and separating waste at the source. Additionally, the negative environmental effects of disposal sites are lessened by lowering the quantity of trash (dry non-recyclables) that must be dumped in landfills. (Sreedevi, 2015)

To encourage recycling and trash segregation practices, appropriate rules and regulations must be vigorously enforced. Adopting policy recommendations from academics that include monetary rewards for reuse and recycling might also be appropriate (Boonrod et al., 2015; Yau, 2010).

Bandura's Social Learning Theory places a strong emphasis on other people's attitudes and emotional responses. In terms of the outcome, the respondent's responses were based on their comprehension of the fundamentals of managing solid waste as presented in the classroom as well as what they had observed. One gets an understanding of how this conduct is carried out by seeing others. This knowledge is then applied to guide decisions in the future. This occurrence is possible through mindful actions and influence from family members and even in the school vicinity.

Table 5. *Level of the Solid Waste Management Practices of the Respondents in Terms of Reduce*

<i>Reduce</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
R1: I borrow, share and/or rent things that are needed occasionally.	2.86	Often
R2: I buy only what I need so that I will not end up throwing away extra food.	3.24	Often
R3: I pack my lunch in reusable lunchbox so that I can't buy wrapped/packed food at school.	3.28	Often
R4: I bring water in reusable water bottles than buying water in one-used plastic bottles at the school.	3.29	Often
R5: I am cautious and responsible to every waste I produced.	3.10	Often
<i>Average</i>	3.15	Often

Note: 1.00-1.79, Never; 1.80-2.59, Seldom; 2.60-3.39, Often; 3.40-4.00, Always

As shown in Table 5, how well solid waste is managed the responders' methods for cutting back. With comments made frequently, the average score is 3.15. Items 4 and 1 had the highest and lowest weighted means, respectively, at 3.29 and often, and 2.86 and often, respectively.

This indicates that the respondents have implemented efficient techniques to reduce solid waste. Additionally, the responders take responsibility for all the garbage they generate and only occasionally bring reusable water bottles to school instead of purchasing single-use plastic bottles.

This aligns with the research of Bautista, (2019) emphasizing that students understand solid waste management. Most of the students knew about Solid Waste Management's administration and policies, but comparatively few knew about their responsibilities as students in applying SWM in practice. The students also dispose of, recycle, and reuse waste products in accordance with excellent solid waste management procedures, even though they only infrequently perform proper segregation and reduction.

The inferential statistics results showed that while the students' level of awareness affected their practices for efficient segregation, reduction, and recycling, it had no effect on how they handled solid waste with regard to reuse or disposal. Bautista (2019).

Table 6. *Level of the Solid Waste Management Practices of the Respondents in Terms of Reuse*

<i>Reuse</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
R1: I reuse my old materials than buying a new one.	3.13	Often
R2: I keep those unfilled papers and used it as scratch.	2.93	Often
R3: I reuse grocery bags.	3.20	Often
R4: I reuse washable containers.	3.20	Often
R5: I reuse scrap paper into memo pads.	2.75	Often
<i>Average</i>	3.04	Often

Note: 1.00-1.79, Never; 1.80-2.59, Seldom; 2.60-3.39, Often; 3.40-4.00, Always

As shown in Table 6, the degree of solid waste management approaches to reuse adopted by the responders. An average weighted mean of 3.04 and frequent remarks are displayed in the result. The largest weighted mean of 3.20 and the most notes received are found in items 3 and 4, respectively, while the lowest weighted mean of 2.75 and the most notes received are found in item 5.

The previously indicated outcome suggests that the participants repurpose solid waste materials in an appropriate way. The responders practiced reusing supermarket bags and washing containers in addition to turning extra paper into memo pads.

When trash reduction is difficult, the focus should be on reusing products as much as possible to lessen the effects on the environment. Products that are repaired, sold, or donated can help reduce waste and promote environmental stewardship at the same time. Reuse stands out as a preferred option over recycling, as it eliminates the need for resource-intensive reprocessing. Moreover, beyond its

environmental benefits, embracing sensitive reuse practices not only fosters community engagement but also promotes social cohesion and cultural preservation, echoing the insights advocated by the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP, 2003).

Table 7. Level of the Solid Waste Management Practices of the Respondents in Terms of Recycling

<i>Recycling</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
R1: I convert or design waste materials into a new product.	2.93	Often
R2: I make decors out of plastic wrappers and other colorful waste materials.	2.84	Often
R3: I ignore importance of recycling.	2.58	Seldom
R4: I initiate generating-income out of waste materials.	2.59	Seldom
Average	2.74	Often

Note: 1.00-1.79, Never; 1.80-2.59, Seldom; 2.60-3.39, Often; 3.40-4.00, Always

As can be seen in Table 7, item number 1 has the highest weighted mean (2.93) with remarks of frequently, while item number 3 has the lowest weighted mean (2.58) with remarks of infrequently. The average weighted mean (2.74) with comments of frequently indicates the respondents' level of solid waste management activities with regard to recycling.

The findings suggested that the respondents recycle waste materials in an efficient manner. Regarding recycling waste materials, the responders are also conscious of its importance. For instance, they are aware that pencil or pen holders can be made from used newspapers and plastic bottles.

According to Victor (2012), recycling is a resource recovery practice which refers to the collection and reusing of waste materials. Recycling is not the sole component of appropriate solid waste management, though. Reducing and reusing materials is also essential. Reducing the quantity of waste materials utilized and beginning to reuse them are necessary for efficient handling of solid waste. With this, one can recycle the waste materials and use it to create a new product.

In light of the outcome, the respondents know the importance of cutting down on solid waste by reducing buying of one-used plastic materials. Through this, the respondents can use their previously bought plastic materials and start re-using it. In addition, the respondents also practiced good ways of creating something useful by recycling solid waste.

Table 8. Level of the Solid Waste Management Practices of the Respondents in Terms of Disposal Practices

<i>Disposal Practices</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
DP1: I throw and left my garbage anywhere.	1.87	Seldom
DP2: I burn waste materials.	2.05	Seldom
DP3: I throw waste materials in common often dumps.	2.47	Seldom
DP4: I dispose biodegradable wastes into a compost pit.	2.75	Often
DP5: I dispose hazardous/toxic/special wastes such as laboratory leftover (chemicals) or electronic waste in any garbage container	1.97	Seldom
Average	2.22	Seldom

Note: 1.00-1.79, Never; 1.80-2.59, Seldom; 2.60-3.39, Often; 3.40-4.00, Always

As shown in Table 8, the extent to which the respondents managed their solid waste using different disposal techniques. The average weighted mean of 2.22 with remarks about rarely is displayed in the result. Item number 4 had the highest weighted mean of 2.75 with comments of frequently falling on it. The least weighted mean, 1.07, indicates that item number 1 was seldom encountered. This indicates that the respondents did, to some extent, dispose of solid trash properly.

Respondents were aware that disposing of biodegradable wastes properly in a compost pit is a good practice. It can be supported through item number 1 of which the respondents are aware that throwing and leaving garbage anywhere is not a good practice. Since the statement connotes negative acts, the answer of the respondents was interpreted as the disposal practices executed by the respondents.

According to Mize (2002), in the Theory of Citizen Participation, emphasis that citizen participation provides individual influence on public decisions and has been a component of democratic public decision-making. Citizen participation encourages public involvement so that the citizens will also perform their roles and responsibilities in the community.

Concerning the result, it is very essential that the respondents also perform their roles and responsibilities in the community by conducting and performing proper waste disposal. They can positively affect their citizens by doing this.

Problem 3: Is there a significant relationship between the level of awareness on solid waste management and the practices on solid waste management of the respondent?

Table 9 presents the relationship between the respondents' solid waste management techniques and their awareness of the subject in terms of knowledge. The results show a statistically significant relationship between the respondents' awareness of solid waste management and their segregation methods. This correlation is observed at the.000 level of significance, which is less than the 0.05 level, meaning that the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that participants should be able to classify waste into categories such as recyclable, non-recyclable, and compostable if they possess a comprehensive understanding of solid waste management.

Based on the data, it can be concluded that there is a significant correlation between the respondents' level of awareness and their lowered behaviors for solid waste management, at a significance level of 0.000, meaning less than 0.05. The null hypothesis is thus disproved. This implies that there's a chance the responders can reduce garbage if they have a sound foundation in solid waste management.

Table 9. *Correlation between the Level of Awareness on Solid Waste Management in Terms of Knowledge and the Practices on the Solid Waste Management of the Respondents*

<i>Solid Waste Management Practices</i>	<i>Level of Awareness On Solid Waste Management in terms of Knowledge</i>		<i>Remarks</i>	
Segregation	Pearson Correlation	Sig. (2-tailed)	.347	Significant
			.000	
		N	110	
Reduce	Pearson Correlation	Sig. (2-tailed)	.368	Significant
			.000	
		N	110	
Reuse	Pearson Correlation	Sig. (2-tailed)	.169	Not Significant
			.077	
		N	110	
Recycling	Pearson Correlation	Sig. (2-tailed)	-.311	Significant
			.001	
		N	110	
Disposal Practices	Pearson Correlation	Sig. (2-tailed)	-.261	Significant
			.006	
		N	110	

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Furthermore, it demonstrates that there is no significant link between the respondents' reuse activities and their degree of awareness regarding solid waste management at the .077 level of significance, which is higher than the 0.05 level. Consequently, there is no rejection of the null hypothesis. This indicates that while the respondents are aware of solid waste management, they are not able to comprehend the concept and implement waste material reuse.

Furthermore, it demonstrates that there is a significant link between the respondents' recycling behaviors and their degree of awareness regarding solid waste management at a significance level of .001, which is less than 0.05. This leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This suggests that the responders can recycle materials if they are knowledgeable about solid waste management.

Additionally, it demonstrates a significant correlation between the respondent's disposal methods and awareness of solid waste management at the .006 level of significance—a level of significance lower than the 0.05 level of significance—supporting the rejection of the null hypothesis. If the respondents are aware of and informed about solid waste management, this implies that they have superior procedures and understand how to dispose of waste items correctly.

Table 10 displays the relationship between the respondents' actions and attitude toward solid waste management and their level of awareness of the subject. The results show a significant relationship between the techniques of segregation, reduction, reuse, and disposal and attitudes toward solid waste management. As a result, the null hypothesis is rejected.

It indicates that the responders have a thorough understanding of appropriate solid waste management. In addition to learning the principles of solid waste management in the classroom, the respondents also put these principles into practice by practicing proper trash segregation, reduction, reuse, and disposal strategies.

Furthermore, this can also be supported based on the previous results as shown on Table 3,4,5 and 7. Table 3 presents the remarks of all respondents, showing that they are adhering to the proper waste segregation protocols. The overall statements shown in Table 4 suggest that respondents are generally conscientious and circumspect when it comes to generating less solid waste. Table 5 indicates that learners possess the ability and awareness to reuse solid waste items with a general comment of frequently.

The general comment of "infrequently" not Table 7 indicates that the respondents are disposing of their trash appropriately, i.e., they are not throwing it anyplace. This result clearly shows that the respondents' practice of maintaining proper solid waste management is significantly influenced by their level of knowledge.

While the respondents recycling practices and level of awareness of the respondents on solid waste does not have significant relationship. However, this does not imply that the respondents are ignorant about the process of recycling solid waste. Table 7 illustrates how unlikely they are to overlook the significance of recycling.

Table 10. *Correlation between the Level of Awareness on Solid Waste Management in Terms of Attitude and the Practices on the Solid Waste Management of the Respondent*

<i>Solid Waste Management Practices</i>	<i>Level of Awareness On Solid Waste Management in terms of Attitude</i>		<i>Remarks</i>
Segregation	Pearson Correlation (2-tailed) N	.319	Significant
		.001	
		110	
Reduce	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.406	Significant
		.000	
		110	
Reuse	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.253	Not Significant
		.008	
		110	
Recycling	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	-.179	Significant
		.061	
		110	
Disposal Practices	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	-.275	Significant
		.004	
		110	

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Problem 4: What action plan can be formulated based from the result of the study?

Propose Action Plan on Solid Waste Management

Rationale

The proposed action plan on solid waste management is designed to encourage more the learners to be more conscious in different issues on our environment regarding on the solid waste thus developing their awareness and practices in order to help minimizing and proper managing of solid waste to conserve and protect our environment.

Objective

The purpose of the action plan is to develop the sense of awareness of the learners enhance their practices in proper handling of solid waste and awaken their interest to help minimizing the waste that they produce.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study and analysis of the study, the following conclusions were formulated:

This study disclosed that respondents were knowledgeable about the solid waste and its effect to human health and to the environment. It is concluded that there is a significant relationship between the level of awareness on solid waste management in terms of knowledge and the segregation, reduce, recycling and disposal practices of the respondent at level of significance which is lesser than 0.05 level thus the null hypothesis is rejected while the level of awareness in terms of knowledge and the reuse practices of the respondents on solid waste management is not significantly correlated since the level of significance is higher than 0.05 level thus, the null hypothesis is accepted.

Moreover, the result reveals that there is a significant relationship between the level of awareness in terms of attitudes and the segregation, reduce, reuse and disposal practices on solid waste management of the respondents since the level of significance does not exceed at 0.05 thus, the null hypothesis is rejected while there is no significant relationship between the level of awareness in terms of attitudes and the recycling practices on solid waste management of the respondents since the level of significance is higher than 0.05 level thus, the null hypothesis is accepted.

Based on the analyses, findings and conclusions obtained in the study, the following recommendations are listed below.

Local Government Units should use the significant findings from this study regarding the solid waste generated by the school. Such information is very important inputs in the development of effective solid waste management plan the municipality.

The school administrators should develop solid waste management programs in their school improvement plan in coordination with the overall municipal solid waste management program.

Community people should be informed about the correct methods of solid waste disposal to prevent undesirable health risk.

Teachers should educate their learners not only about the environmental hazards generated by improper disposal of solid waste but also teach the process of recycling and reusing of solid waste management.

Learners should actively participate in the implementation of solid waste management activities both in the school and into the community.

Future researcher should conduct further study regarding solid waste management in educational institutions to assure its inclusion as effective elements in school improvement plan.

The action plan as an output of the study should be implemented.

References

Ahmad, J., Noor, S. M., & Ismail, N. (2015). Investigating students' environmental knowledge, attitude, practice and communication. *Asian Social Science*, 11(16), 284.

Ajzen, Icek. (1991). The theory of planned behavior. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 50, 179-211. 10.1016/0749-5978(91)90020-T. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/272790646_The_Theory_of_Planned_Behavior

Anitha, M. (2017). A study on awareness of domestic solid waste among high school students. *IOSR Journal of Environmental Science, Toxicology and Food Technology*, 11, 43-48. 10.9790/2402-1105024348. Retrieved from <http://www.iosrjournals.org/iosr-jestft/papers/vol11-issue%205/Version-2/F1105024348.pdf>

Antonangeli, T. (2018). Different methods of disposal. Retrieved from <https://www.hunker.com/13420834/different-methods-of-waste-disposal>

Atalia, K. R., Buha, D. M., Bhavsar, K. A., Shah, N. K. A review on composting of municipal solid waste. Retrieved from <https://www.iosrjournals.org/iosr-jestft/papers/vol9-issue5/Version-1/D09512029.pdf>

Atienza, V. A. (2011). The waste management system in the Philippines: Initiatives to promote waste segregation and recycling through good governance. Retrieved from <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/of-the-Waste-Management-System-in-the-Philippines-%3A-Atienza/cf47f619c46998570d9b7d54d23f6b1591baa367>

Bandura, A. (1977). *Social learning theory*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice Hall.

Barton, D. C. (1990). *Clayey barrier system for waste disposal* (4th ed.). Chicago: Publishing Company Inc.

Bautista, P. (2019). Level of awareness and practices on solid waste management (SWM) among college students. Retrieved from <https://innspub.net/level-of-awareness-and-practices-on-solid-waste-management-swm-among-college-students/>

Boonrod, K., Towprayoon, S., Bonnet, S., & Tripetchkul, S. (2015). Enhancing organic waste separation at the source behavior: A case study of the application of motivation mechanisms in communities in Thailand. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 95(3), 77-90. Retrieved from <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/27658511.2021.1935532>

Botkins, D., & Keller, E. (2003). *Environmental science: Earth as a living planet* (4th ed.). New York: John Wiley and Sons, Inc.

Castillo, A., & Otoma, S. (2013). Status of solid waste management in the Philippines. Retrieved from https://www.jstage.jst.go.jp/article/jsmcwm/24/0/24_677/_pdf/

Danthurebandara, M., Passel, S., Nelen, D., Tielemans, Y., & Van Acker, K. (2013). Environmental and socio-economic impacts of landfills. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/278738702_Environmental_and_socio-economic_impacts_of_landfills

Dataman, A., Amparado, R., Aranico, E., Torres, M. A., & Demayo, C. (2012). Assessment of solid waste management in the Islamic City of Marawi, Philippines. *International Journal of Environmental Science and Development*, 3(6), 465-469. 10.7763/IJESD.2012.V3.268. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/269839285_Assessment_of_Solid_Waste_Management_in_the_Islamic_City_of_Marawi_Philippines

Department of Environment and Natural Resources. (2012). *Managing our solid waste: An overview of the ecological solid waste management act*. Retrieved November 4, 2016 from: <http://119.92.161.2/embgovph/eed/Resources/FactSheets/tabid/139aid/195/Default.aspx>

Galarpe, V. R. K. (2017). Review on the impacts of waste disposal sites in the Philippines. *Science International*, 29, 379-385. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/316598058_Review_on_the_Impacts_of_Waste_Disposal_Sites_in_the_Philippines

Galarpe, V. R. K., & Heyasa, B. B. (2017). Solid waste management response of selected public secondary school science teachers.

International Journal of Advanced and Applied Sciences, 4, 110-115. 10.21833/ijaas.2017.07.016. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/317637490_Solid_waste_management_response_of_selected_public_secondary_school_science_teachers/citation/download

Kaliyaperumal, K. (2004). Guideline for conducting a knowledge, attitude and practice (KAP) study. Retrieved from http://v2020eresource.org/content/files/guideline_kap_Jan_mar04.pdf

Magallanes, K. H. (2011). Improper solid waste management in Iligan City, Philippines. Retrieved from <https://www.scribd.com/document/316157148/Improper-Solid-Waste-Management-in-Iligan-City-Philippines>

Mansur, A. (2015). Plasma gasification as an alternative technology for the treatment of waste in Kano State, Nigeria: A proposed model. Retrieved from <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/a996/ebb9ef91511c3ecf431e9b9b95372a4cd644.pdf>

Mawis. (2019). Solid waste mismanagement in the Philippines. Retrieved from <https://business.inquirer.net/270819/solid-waste-mismanagement-in-the-philippines#ixzz64NP5Nzpc>

McAllister, J. (2015). Factors influencing solid-waste management in the developing world. All Graduate Plan B and Other Reports, Paper 528. Retrieved from <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/8075/9dc84d63dbcc356fc66045e1055d75c5cac1.pdf>

Mondal, P. (2016). Six main types of solid waste management. Retrieved October 11, 2016 from: <http://www.yourarticlelibrary.com/solid-waste/6-main-types-of-solid-waste-management/30162>

Oh, J. H. (2013). Research in ecology, Manila Philippines: American Psychological Association. Retrieved from <http://slideshare.net/jisseah/chapter-i-16274129>

Paghasian, M. C. (2017). Awareness and practices on solid waste management among college students in Mindanao State University Maigo School of Arts and Trades. 10.2991/icet-17.2017.2. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/320202045_Awareness_and_Practices_on_Solid_Waste_Management_among_College_Students_in_Mindanao_State_University_Maigo_School_of_Arts_and_Trades

Paragoso, G., Sapar, C. M., Magsayo, J., Lahoylahoy, M., & Guarin, R. M. (2018). Solid waste management in Linamon, Lanao del Norte. AIP Conference Proceedings, 1923, 030034. 10.1063/1.5019525. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/322290022_Solid_waste_management_in_Linamon_Lanao_del_Norte

Perez, D. (2011). Best practices on solid waste management of Nepalese cities. Retrieved from <http://apjeas.apjmr.com/wpcontent/uploads/2014/09/APJEAS--2014-1-056.pdf>

Prakriti, Centre for Management Studies. (2006). Solid waste management principles and terminologies. Retrieved October 11, 2016 from: http://cmsdu.org/organs/solid_waste_management.pdf

Ramos, J. N., & Pecajas, E. S. (2016). Knowledge, attitudes and practices in solid waste management among the secondary schools in the Division of Leyte. Retrieved from <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/KNOWLEDGE-%2C-ATTITUDES-AND-PRACTICES-IN-SOLID-WASTE-Ramos-Pecajas/38783d757932fc6afb55b2daa3541dba0558bc38>

Reyes, P. V., & Furto, M. V. (2013). Greening of the solid waste management in Batangas City. Retrieved from https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/1870/240294c592d5af0dba91718fbca236ec004e.pdf?_ga=2.228442589.1344012468.1567474972-155340205.1567474972

Samiha, B. (2013). The importance of the 3R principle of municipal solid waste management for achieving sustainable development. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/287318675_The_Importance_of_the_3R_Principle_of_Municipal_Solid_Waste_Management_for_Achieving_Sustainable_Development/fulltext/569dd51408ae950bd7a6b5c6/The-Importance-of-the-3R-Principle-of-Municipal-Solid-Waste-Management-for-Achieving-Sustainable-Development.pdf

Sreedevi, S. (2015). Solid waste generation and its management: A case study. Retrieved from <https://www.isca.me/IJENS/Archive/v4/i1/15.ISCA-IRJEvS-2014-260.pdf>

Swafford, L. (2015). Practicing the '7 R's' lifestyle. Retrieved from https://www.dailycitizen.news/news/lifestyles/practicing-the-r-s-lifestyle/article_9afb2524-e91e-11e4-a208-bb1680190d92.html

Suhaib, A. (2019). Waste disposal methods: Perspective for Africa. Retrieved from <https://www.bioenergyconsult.com/waste-disposal-methods-africa/>

United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP). (2003). A manual for water and waste management: What the tourism industry can do to improve its performance. United Nations Publication. ISBN: 92-807-2343-x, pp. 3-13.

Uwamwezi, G. (2015). Knowledge, attitude and practices on waste management in selected secondary schools in Westlands Sub-

- County, Nairobi County. Retrieved from http://erepository.uonbi.ac.ke/bitstream/handle/11295/104184/Grace_Uwamwezi_FINAL_THESIS.PDF?sequence=4&isAllowed=y
- Victor, A. (2012). Refuse management. Retrieved from <https://vcadeworks.blogspot.com/2012/06/refuse-management.html>
- Yau, Y. (2010). Domestic waste recycling, collective action and economic incentive: The case in Hong Kong. *Waste Management*, 30(12), 2440–2447. Retrieved from <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/27658511.2021.1935532>
- World Bank. (2001). *Philippines environment monitor 2001*. Washington, DC: World Bank. Retrieved from <http://documents.worldbank.org/curated/en/756271468776393945/Philippines-environment-monitor-2001>

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